

Can rural youth farm their ways out of poverty? Experience from vocational skills in Uganda

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Abstract

The government of Uganda adopted vocational skilling as one of its strategy of addressing youth unemployment. However, youth vocational aspiration has been biased against agriculture. Using a three-year cohort tracer study, I show that agribusiness (29%) lifted more graduate youth out of extreme poverty than services/trade (12%) and manufacturing (22%) sectors. I therefore recommend a deliberate targeting of agricultural vocational training, as well as the re-orientation of Business, Technical, and Vocational Education and Trainings (BTVETs) institutions to youth training in strategic high-impact agro-enterprises so that agriculture attracts and provides decent employment for rural youth.

Key words

Youth unemployment, Agriculture, Poverty reduction

1.0 Introduction

Uganda is experiencing an alarming rate of youth unemployment. In response the government and its development partners have adopted vocational skilling as a quick solution to self-employment and youth poverty reduction. However, the vocational aspirations of many youth is biased against agricultural vocational training. Many youths prefer vocational skilling in services and manufacturing labour market courses. In this paper, I question this negative assumption by asking, “can agricultural vocational skilling lift graduate youth out of extreme poverty?” I use a three-year cohort tracer study of 452 vocational skilling graduates in rural West Nile, Uganda.

This paper is organized as follows. It starts by presenting the youth employment challenges in Uganda. This is followed by a description of Uganda’s response to youth joblessness. The paper then presents the asset poverty measurement method used to collect and analyze data. It then ends with a discussion of the results and recommendations especially by raising concerns on agriculture that the government has greatly ignored in its skewed pursuit for a middle-income country.

2.0 Youth employment challenges

The ILO *World Employment Social Outlook Trends 2015* estimates a deteriorating global employment. In 2014, the report estimated that more than 201 million people were unemployed and closing this employment gap would require additional 280 million jobs by 2019. Youth, as a social category, suffer most from this alarming unemployment status given that the number of unemployed youth globally increased from 70 million in 2007 to 74 million in 2014 (ILO, 2015).

A similar trend of youth unemployment is evident in Uganda where in spite of the low (4.7%) annual growth in total labour force, only 18.5% of the total labour force is in waged employment and 81.5% are self-employed (GoU, 2015). While 800,000 people annually enter the labour market, the net job creation is a dismal 10% (MoES, 2011). The 2014 Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) highly acclaimed entrepreneurial capability (i.e. 36% total early-stage entrepreneurial activity) in the country (Guloba and Gardiner, 2015) has not helped the unemployment situation. Youth who constitute 21% of the total population and 57% of the labour force are predominantly employed in non-wage employment (GoU, 2015: 4). The 2013 school-to-work

survey (STWS) shows that informal employment account for 92% of youth employment. It further asserts that Ugandan youth undergo a very slow labour transition process as many youths who complete their transition spend an average of 17.1 months unemployed, 19.1 months in temporary employment, and 38.3 months in self-employment (Byamugisha, et al., 2014: 36-45).

In West Nile region (where this study draws its data), the second poorest in the country next to Karamoja, youth unemployment is exceptionally high. Less than two percent of youth have access to wage employment leaving majority engaged in subsistence agriculture. Not surprising 80% of youth in the region live on less than US\$ 1.25 per day compared to the national average of 65% and 34% in central region (UBOS, 2012). It is, therefore, common sight to see many redundant youths by the roadsides and in the mushrooming trading centers drinking alcohol, playing cards and “omweso” or smoking marijuana. However, this situation is not about to change soon: Fox and Sohnesen (2012) estimated that it will take one generation before majority of the labour force has a non-farm salary job.

Many factors account for the above deplorable youth unemployment situation. Foremost, formal jobs in Uganda are found in urban areas. Two-thirds of all jobs created in 2001-2011 were confined to only six out of the 112 districts and mainly in central Uganda (MoFPED, 2013). Yet access to formal jobs in Uganda is known to require family, tribal, religious, and political connections; there are key social assets that many rural youth lack. Worse still, formal sector employers have a consistent preference for university over secondary school graduates besides wrongly “perceiving youth not only to be unprepared to work in terms of skills, qualifications, and experience but also as impatient, demanding, unreliable, and driven by the desire for quick money” (Butler and Kebba, 2014: 17; Banks and Sulaiman, 2012, 57).

In addition, the Uganda Youth Map Study 2011 attributes the high youth unemployment to the mismatch of education to labour market needs (International Youth Foundation, 2011). For rural youth, Business, Technical, and Vocational Education and Trainings (BTVETs) are hardly accessible: these institutions are urban based, they prefer to enroll those with O' level education, and they charge high fees (MoES, World Bank and BTC Uganda, 2011). More so, many rural youths lack sufficient experiences and skills for formal labour market. This gap, the Second National Development Plan (NDPII 2015-20) (GoU, 2015: 200) and ILO (2005) note that are due to inadequate

internships, apprenticeships, voluntary work or paid work, vocational guidance and counseling, and poor job placement mechanisms. Finally, many rural youth lack access to business finance. Commercial banks are out of their reach given that these institutions are urban based and mandatorily secure their credits with collateral that the youth lack. Meanwhile the Youth Venture Fund setup by government has largely remained urban and targeted at microenterprises other than agriculture (Ahaibwe, 2014).

In spite of the alluded limited labour market demand factors, many rural youths still prefer modern sector jobs. The Youth Watch 2012 report shows in Table 1 the wide job aspiration-expectation gaps. While many youths aspire for non-farm businesses (48%) and salaried jobs (31%), many also end up in subsistence farming and casual wage employment. This gap is in line with the findings of Nwagwu (1976: 113) that African youth prefer professional, white-collar and supervisory work contrary to the job market realities. He notes that such aspiration shows that many youths live in a “make-belief world with vaulting ambitions, obsessional preference, and prestige conscious attitude.”

Agriculture is perceived by many youth as a matter of survival. The sector is stigmatized as a low status job for those who have failed to make it in life. Youth distaste for employment in the agricultural sector is also fueled by many factors. Parents control subsistence agriculture and thus few youth (less than 6%) make decisions on farm work and the crops to grow (Butler and Kebba, 2014: 17-18). More so, subsistence farming is less profitable and has few role model agripreneurs that many youths can look up to and emulate their success stories.

Table 1: Percent distribution of job aspiration –expectation gap

<i>Job market</i>	<i>Jobs preferred to be doing (%)</i>	<i>Job likely to be doing (%)</i>	<i>Aspiration-expectation gap (%)</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
Subsistence farming	9	23	-14	Low aspiration; High expectation
Casual wage	5	12	-7	Low aspiration; High expectation
Commercial farming	6	7	-1	Low aspiration; Low expectation
Non-farm business	48	34	+14	High aspiration; Low expectation
Salaried	31	24	+7	High aspiration; Low expectation

Source: Banks and Sulaiman (2009: Figure 38; p.62).

3.0 Uganda's Response to Youth joblessness

Jobs are known to provide individuals with a sense of personal purpose and satisfaction (World Bank, 2012). Productive jobs are even better means to sustain economic growth, reduce poverty, achieve structural transformation, and prevent social and political upheavals (MoFPED 2014). Thus, youth employment, the ILO's *Youth: Pathways to Decent Work emphasizes*, is good for everyone: For government it improves revenue and poverty reduction; for employers' organization, it boasts increased consumptions and personal savings; for workers' organizations, it increases membership and voice; and for the youth, it improves citizenship and wellbeing (ILO, 2005: 6-7). Therefore, a high youth unemployment rate is too costly for society. To the youth, it bears considerable personal and social costs such as decreased life satisfaction and stigmatization (ILO, 2014: 25). For the economy, Banks and Sulaiman (2012) estimated the cost of youth unemployment in Uganda at UGX 356.4 billion (\$142.6 million) annually. This annual loss is a considerable missed development opportunity given that it is equivalent to the cost for the provision of 300 furnished 4-classroom blocks for about 50,000 pupils and mud drilling of 10,000 boreholes to provide access to safe water for 10 million people.

In anticipation of the youth dividend, the government of Uganda adopted a three-pronged approach, namely: (a) Enterprise development through access to finance such as the Youth Venture

Fund, Graduate Venture Fund, and Youth Livelihood Programme; (b) Strengthening private sector investment through improved enabling environment for more job creation; and (c) Youth skilling programmes through entrepreneurship and vocational training. The priority attention given to strategic investment in human capital development explains why in part the Ministry of Education and Sports developed the BTVET Strategic Plan - Skilling Uganda (2011-2020), which seeks to align education to labour market demands and to engage the private sector in quality education provision in an inclusive, short, cost-effective, and practical manner. BTVET is desired in the short term to match skills to market needs thus creating a quick pathway into employment, income generation, and better wellbeing (Filmer and Fox, et al, 2014). In support, government spending on skills development increased from UGX 50 billion in 2005/06 to UGX 70 billion in 2013/14 and the cost per student in public BTVET institutions increased between UGX 1.5 million and UGX 3.5 million (MoFPED, 2014: 26, 30).

However, Skilling Uganda has received skewed implementation. The government, donor community, private sector, and civil society organizations are providing biased vocational skills for youth. Most of the courses sponsored are in the services sector (hair dressing, phone repairs, motor mechanics) and artisanal and light manufacturing activities (carpentry, tailoring and knitting, bakery, blacksmithing, metal works, soap making). Agribusiness is less targeted. A random survey of 14 BTVET institutions in West Nile region, Uganda indicated that in 2015 out of 701 students enrolled only 9% were pursuing agribusiness as compared to 50% in services and 41% in manufacturing labour market related courses. As is noted above, many youths do not consider agriculture as an employment opportunity. For instance, in 2014 during the SNV-Netherlands Development Organization funded Opportunity for Youth Employment Project public dialogue meeting many youths asked, “if farming the way our parents did failed to lift them out of poverty, why should we waste time in it?” Many echo that agriculture does not provide a pathway out of poverty. However, aware that agriculture employs seven in ten people in Uganda and nine in ten people in rural Uganda, such a distaste presents not only a missed employment opportunity, it also aggravates the unemployment challenge. Yet to date there is no evidence to support or counteract this negative assertion. To test the validity of this youth perception against agriculture we ask a central question: “Can agricultural vocational skilling lift graduate youth out of extreme poverty?”

4.0 Asset poverty measurement

To answer the above question three issues were important. First, I designed the study to use the asset poverty measurement approach. This is because productive assets more than income alone are critical for securing rural livelihoods. As Bebbington (1999) notes, assets are vehicles for making a living meaningful and challenging the structures under which one makes a living. These multidimensional values of assets make them a better measure of wealth (or poverty). Many livelihood studies confirm that assets represent the stock of wealth (Sherraden, 1991) that: regulates current and future consumption (Beverly, et al 2008); provides security against and resilience to shocks and stresses (Rank and Hirschl 2010); triggers breaking intergenerational poverty (Cheng and Page-Adams, 1996); and are a basis for business growth and sustainability.

The asset poverty concept as introduced by Haveman and Wolff (2004: 145) is a measure of household economic ability to meet its current and future consumption. It

measures the extent to which households have stock of asset which is sufficient to sustain a basic needs level of consumption during temporary hard times (of three months or 25% threshold).

To this Leonard and Di (2012: 1-2) elongate the time period to 9-months (or 75% threshold) because “asset accumulation at levels equal to nine-months’ worth of the required consumption income at the income poverty level enables a family’s to permanently escape poverty.” The approach categorizes households or individuals according to how their asset values can sufficiently enable them to live at the minimum income poverty level (i.e., US\$ 1.25 per person per day). To do so, first, the approach estimates a “household/individual net worth or asset wealth” by summing “liquid assets” – cash or financial assets and “productive asset” – tangible assets that can be disposed of as and when the need arises. Second, it computes the extent to which a household/individual net worth/asset wealth meets the current household consumption needs at the international poverty line of US\$ 1.25 (or UGX 3,125 – 2005 price) per person per day. While a single person household would need UGX 1,140,625 million per annum to live at the poverty line, this value would increase by the number of people in a household. Households with many people would therefore require more net worth/asset wealth to sustain their livelihoods. Finally, the measurement approach classifies households according to how their asset wealth can sufficiently enable them to live

at the minimum income poverty level. While a household is poor if its net worth is unable to meet its consumption needs over a 3-month period, it is considered non-poor if its net worth is able to meet its 9-month consumption needs. To this category, we add the resilient households/individuals who have the net worth that makes them neither poor nor non-poor.

Second, a tracer study approach was used to collect data (Macci, Jenny, and Wilhem, 2009). A list of 602 youths (15-30 years) who benefited from non-formal BTVET training in the last 3 years was secured from the Agency for Accelerated Regional Development (AFARD), a civil society organization, in West Nile districts of Nebbi, Yumbe and Moyo in Uganda. These youths received a “free-course choice” 1- 6 months non-formal training that covers vocational, business management, and life skills training. Most of the trainings offered were in services (hair dressing), light manufacturing (carpentry, tailoring and knitting, bakery, and soap making) and agribusiness (of both crops and livestock). Upon completion of the training each graduate was provided a start-up kit to start and grow his/her own enterprise. A quantitative survey questionnaire was administered face-to-face to 452 youth (within 18-30 years age bracket). Information was collected to cover both baseline and current business status. Finally, a follow-up data collection phase was conducted only among graduate youth engaged in agribusiness with due attention to their enterprise profitability analysis.

5.0 Characteristics of graduates

Data was collected from 452 self-employed youths who were within the youth age bracket of 18-30 year. These youths were drawn from Moyo (32%), Nebbi (28%), and Yumbe (40%) districts. Of this total, 48% males and 52% females. While 49% were single, 51% were married. However, only 18% were living alone and caring for themselves. Many youth (82%) had dependents and were living in households with an average of 2 people.

These youths were trained in services (42%), manufacturing (38%), and agribusiness (20%) labour market courses. However, at the time of the study 12% of those trained in manufacturing courses abandoned their sectors and were self-employed in agribusiness. This finding confirms the results of Youth Watch 2012 that many youth exhibits dynamic labour market practices through switching between and within sectors depending on their local market conditions. It also shows the low opinion youth have towards agribusiness labour market.

Table 2 below shows that the graduate youth enterprises are growing. At the start, graduate youth in manufacturing sector markets invested more than their counterparts (UGX 114,095 and UGX 137,220) in services and agribusiness sector markets respectively. The youth enterprises have also created employment opportunities for at least one more non-trained youth. There is also no marked difference in the number of hours and days worked daily and weekly in the different sector markets. However, it is evident that within 3 years the growth rate was much higher in agribusiness (373%) than in manufacturing (289%), and services (50%) sector markets. In addition, there is a 2% point higher income/wage share paid by agribusiness than the other sector markets.

Table 2: Characteristics of graduate youth businesses by sector labour markets

	<i>Sectors labour markets</i>			
	Agribusiness	Services	Manufacturing	Total
Proportion of youth employed	31.6	42.3	26.1	100.0
Average start-up capital (UGX)	461,483	484,608	598,703	507,078
Average current business value (UGX)	2,181,803	728,639	2,328,723	1,606,100
Average monthly income (UGX)	2,772,889	2,719,451	2,504,129	2,680,145
Average number of hired employees	1.1	0.9	1.5	1.1
Average number of hours worked daily	7.1	7.1	7.2	7.1
Average number of days worked weekly	6.0	6.0	6.0	6.0
Average monthly wages per employee (UGX)	173,137	110,178	99,203	127,231
Average monthly wages/income (%)	6.2	4.1	4.0	4.7

5.1 Asset wealth status of graduate youth

Table 3 below shows that within the last 3-years, graduate youth increased their net worth by 342%. Many graduate youths were able to access debts even if the debt values were very small. They were also able to increase their financial assets. However, more than 96% of the total net worth increase was in productive assets. Contrary to the negative belief held by youth against agriculture, the graduate youth of agribusiness had higher gains in net worth (554%) than those in the manufacturing (411%) and services (152%). This gain in net worth for agribusiness graduates indicates a difference of 143-399% above their counterparts in manufacturing and services sector markets.

Table 3: Average change in asset values by sector labour markets

	<i>Sector labour markets</i>							
	Agribusiness		Services		Manufacturing		Total	
	UGX	%	UGX	%	UGX	%	UGX	%
Financial assets	183,956	319	62,010	139	159,761	348	126,109	257
Productive assets	1,626,769	609	502,152	161	1,473,220	441	1,111,458	366
Debt	33,442	847	30,595	746	84,106	2,601	45,466	1,188
Total net worth	1,777,283	554	533,566	152	1,548,875	411	1,192,101	342

5.2 Poverty status of graduate youth

Within the three years of self-employment, the graduate youths have moved out of extreme poverty. Table 4 below shows that overall 20% of the self-employed youth exited out of extreme poverty. However, majority of those who moved out of poverty were the graduate youth

of agribusiness (28%) followed by those in manufacturing (22%) and least for services (12%) sector labour markets.

Table 4: Distribution of youth poverty by business sector (%)

<i>Sector labour markets</i>	<i>Asset poverty status</i>		
	Before	After	Difference
Agribusiness	91.6	62.9	-28.7
Services	92.7	80.6	-12.1
Manufacturing	96.6	74.6	-22.0
Total	93.4	73.5	-19.9

5.3 Poverty dynamics and sector labour markets

Figure 1: Poverty dynamics among graduate youth

Although table 4 above shows that many graduate youth (74%) are still stuck in extreme poverty, 26% are not poor. To explore the movement out of poverty, Figure 1 shows that within 3-year period many graduate youth of agribusiness (33%) compared to manufacturing (24%) and services (18%) sector labour markets moved out of extreme poverty. This relatively high exit out of extreme poverty for agribusiness graduate youth explains why only 59% of them remained poor compared to their colleagues in manufacturing (73%) and services (76%) sector labour markets.

5.4 Exploring the agricultural pathways out of poverty

All the results above indicate that graduate youth of agricultural vocational training out performed their counterparts. They had higher growth rate in their business values (373%) and more net worth gains (554%) that without doubt saw 33% exit out of extreme poverty. These findings dispel the doubts many youths have that agriculture cannot lift them out of poverty. Yet with 63% of graduate youth stuck in extreme poverty it is also evident that not all agribusiness opportunities are able to provide decent employment for youth to exit poverty. If youth should buy-in the agribusiness employment opportunities, they will therefore need to join the profitable subsectors that will earn them the income with which they can gain their prestige.

Further, analyzing the various agribusinesses graduate youth were undertaking in order to find out their economic viability for poverty reduction, collected data on the production and marketing costs as well as the current sales prices. While for crops the average

production level was one acre, for poultry it was a cock with eight pullets and for piggery a boar with ten gilts. Each enterprise was subjected to a one-year return cycle. The profit margins were tested to assess whether or not they could guarantee an income with which a youth agri-preneur (with an average of 2 persons) can live above the various poverty line (UGX 3,193,750 for \$1.25/daily; UGX 5,110,000 for \$2/daily, and UGX 12,775,000 for \$5 daily).

Figure 2 shows that by relying on gross margin analysis only, all the enterprises the graduate youth were undertaking have positive net incomes. However, by subjecting these enterprises' profits to the basic livelihood needs it stands out that a number of enterprises can hardly enable youth to live above the US \$1.25 per person daily. This included crop enterprises (such as soy beans, sun flower, broad beans, and simsim) and poultry rearing. When the consumption bar is increased to US \$2 per person daily, rice and Irish potato had low profit margins that failed test. At US \$5 per person daily, it was only onions, cabbages, and piggery that passed the test.

This finding shows that although a number of crop and livestock enterprises are being promoted, the narrow focus on profitability analysis rather than on their poverty reduction potentials makes many youths to enter such sub-sector labour markets only to get stuck in poverty. For instance, for a youth to earn a profit that can guarantee their livelihood about the extreme poverty line (\$.12), s/he would need to farm 3.1 acres of soy beans, 6 acres of sun flower, 2.5 acres of broad beans, and 8 acres of simsim. These are large tracks of land that many youths do not have, besides being inspired to farm.

Figure 2: Poverty reduction potentials of various agricultural enterprises

6.0 Discussion and Recommendations

This paper has explored the rising youth unemployment rate and how governments and development partners are responding with vocational skilling as a quick-fix solution. In Uganda, the strategic plan for Skilling Uganda was developed and it is being up-scaled. This is rightly premised on existing evidences that technical and vocational skills training complemented with entrepreneurship education and start-up kits increases self-employment, incomes and wellbeing (Cho and Honorati, 2013; Tripney, et al, 2013). However, that youth have distaste for agricultural employment, many prefer to train in courses for services and manufacturing sector labor markets. The neglect for agriculture is however based on unfounded evidence. Youth, including those who lack the skills and social networks for formal employment, simply perceive that agriculture is a dirty job meant for those who have failed in life and cannot lift them out of poverty. To them, to be employed in agriculture is an automatic license for living one's life in dire poverty. I questioned this assumption by assessing whether agricultural vocational skilling lift graduate youth out of extreme poverty? The findings show that 12% of those trained in manufacturing courses shifted from their sector labour market into agribusiness. For all these self-employed graduate youth, those who were employed in agribusiness sector labour market attained higher (i) business value growth of 373% compared to those in manufacturing (289%), and services (50%); (ii) asset net worth of 554% compared to those in the manufacturing (411%) and services (152%); and (iii) proportion of those who moved out of extreme poverty of 33% compared to manufacturing (24%) and services (18%).

These evidences demonstrate the missed employment and development opportunity in agricultural sector for rural youth who are unable to access the urban biased formal employment opportunities. It also raises the question of how vocational skilling opportunities are being provided. The enrolment data shows that there is inability to address the biases against agriculture. The detailed agri-enterprise poverty reduction analysis further reveals that often many youths are trained in agro-enterprise that can hardly lift them out of poverty.

Thus, agriculture has a huge untapped potential for increasing decent employment opportunity for rural youth. The West Nile region, in

particular, and Uganda in general, has a huge agricultural potential for rural development. The climate is suitable for almost all crop and livestock enterprises; soils are fertile; the rapid rate of urbanization (7% per annum) provides ready markets; land and labor are readily available. Many feeder roads are motorable and provide low transaction cost and ready access to the market.

However, as it is evident from this study, there is need to change the mindset of many youth towards agricultural employment through the provision of “occupational guidance and counseling” (Nwagwu, 1976: 113). Additionally, in order to meet the needs of youth for “quick and high income and social prestige” there is need to target their agricultural vocational training to high-impact agro-enterprises. BTVET institutions (and the various local governments of the areas) need to conduct a rigorous analysis of the most suitable agro-enterprises in their areas bearing in mind not only gross margin analysis, but most importantly the poverty reduction potentials of such enterprises. Butler and Kebba (2014: 32) advice that such sub-sectors to be targeted should be those that: (i) require little capital, land and finance; (ii) have a fast turnaround time to earnings; and (iii) do not require the drudgery associated with subsistence farming. Finally, it is important to echo that there is need for central government to prioritize agriculture in its budget allocation. Four independent studies (MoAAIF 2009a-e; Action Aid Uganda, 2010; PELUM Uganda 2010; and Lukwago, 2010) show that the underfunding and poor performance of the sector is a lost opportunity for poverty reduction and socio-economic transformation. Since 1991, the government has hardly allocated 5% of its budget to agriculture contrary to CAADP (10%) target that would inevitably grow the economy by 6.3% per annum and reduce poverty level by 6.1%. Thus, to guarantee success of youths in agriculture, government needs to address the critical needs for capital to boost production, market to increase profit, and insurance to buffer risks (Butler and Kebba, 2014: 32).

References

- Action Aid Uganda (2010) Invest in Smallholder Farmers: Six Areas for Improvement in Agricultural Financing. Grand Brand Ltd: Kampala.
- Ahaibwe, G. (2014) Creating Youth Employment through Entrepreneurship Financing: Is the Uganda Youth Venture Capital Fund on Course? Kampala: EPRC.
- Banks, N., and Sulaiman, M. (2012) Problem or Promise? Harnessing Youth Potential in Uganda. BRAC and Mastercard Foundation.
- Bebbington, A. (1999). Capitals and capabilities: A framework for analysing peasant viability, rural livelihoods and poverty. *World Development*, 27(12), 2021-2044.
- Beverly, S., Sherraden, M., Zhan, M., Shanks, T.R.W., Nam, Y., and Cramer, R. (2008) Determinants of Asset Building. Washington, DC: The Urban Institute, Center for Social Development, and The New American Foundation.
- Butler, E., and Kebba, A. (2014) Youth and Agriculture in Uganda: An Assessment. Combining Agriculture Improvements and Youth Development Shows Promise for Both. QED Group, LLC. USAID.
- Byamugisha, J., Shamchiyeva, L., and Kizu, T. (2014) Labour Market Transition of Young Women and Men in Uganda. Work4Youth Publication Series No. 22. Geneva: ILO. (pp. 2-4)
- Cheng, L., and Page-Adams, D. (1996) Education, Assets, and Intergenerational Well-Being: The Case of Female Headed Families. Working Paper No. 96-3. Washington University in St. Louis: Center for Social Development.
- Cho, Y., and Honorati, M. (2013) Entrepreneurship Programs in Developing Countries: A Meta Regression Analysis. Policy Research Working paper 6402. Washington, DC: The World Bank.
- Filmer, D. and Fox, L. with Brooks, K., Goyal, A., Mengistae, T., Premand, P., Ringold, D., Sharma, S., and Zorya, S. (2014) Youth Employment in Sub-Saharan Africa. Overview. Washington, D.C.: The World Bank.

- Fox, L., and Sohnesen, T.P. (2012) "Household Enterprises in Sub-Saharan Africa. Why They Matter for Growth, Jobs and Livelihoods." Policy Research Working Paper 6184. Washington, DC: The World Bank.
- GoU (2015) Second National Development Plan (NDP II) 2015-20. Kampala: National Planning Authority.
- Guloba, M.M. and Gardiner, D. (2015) Youth Entrepreneurship in Uganda: Policy, Evidence and Stakeholder. A Context Analysis. Kampala: EPRC and ILO.
- Haveman, R., and Wolff, E.N. (2004) "The Concept and Measurement of Asset Poverty: Levels, Trends, and Composition for the US, 1983-2001." *Journal of Economic Inequality*, 2(2) 145-169.
- ILO (2005). Youth: Pathways to Decent Work. Report IV. Promoting Youth Employment – Tackling The Challenge. International Labour Conference, 93rd Session, 2005. Geneva: ILO.
- ILO (2014) Global Employment Trends 2014: Risk of a Jobless Recovery? Geneva: ILO.
- ILO (2015) Global Employment Trends 2015: Sacling Up Investments in Decent Jobs for Youth. Geneva: ILO.
- International Youth Foundation (2011) YouthMap Uganda: Navigating Challenges. Charting Hope. A Cross-sector Situation Analysis on Youth in Uganda. Executive Version.
- Konrad-Adenauer Stiftung (2011) Employment Policies for Uganda: Young Leaders Perspectives. A Study Conducted by the Young Leaders Think Tank for Policy Alternatives. Kampala.
- Leonard, T., and Di, W. (2012) Reentering Asset Poverty After an Exit: Evidence from the PSID. Research Department Working Paper 1204. Federal Reserve Bank of Dallas.
- Lukwago, D. (2010) Increasing Agricultural Sector Financing: Why it Matters for Uganda's Socio-economic Transformation. ACODE Policy Research Series, No. 40. Kampala: ACODE.
- Macci, M., Jenny, B., and Wilhelm, K. (2009) Measuring Education's Path to Prosperity: Tracer Studies for Vocational Education and Training Programmes – A Practical Tool Kit 7. Zurich: Helvatas.

- MoAAIF (2009) Uganda: Agricultural Growth and Poverty Reduction. Past Performance and Prospective Outcomes. CAADP. Brochure 3. Entebbe: MoAAIF, IFPRI, and COMESA Secretariat.
- MoES (2011) Skilling Uganda – Strategic Plan 2011-20. Kampala.
- MoES, World Bank and BTC Uganda (2011) BTVET Delivery, Technical Annex of the BTVET Sub-sector Analysis. Kampala
- MoFPED (2013) Millennium Development Goals Report for Uganda 2013. Special Theme: Drivers of MDG Progress in Uganda and Implications for the Post-2015 Development Agenda. Kampala: MoFPED.
- MoFPED (2014) Uganda’s Employment Challenge: An Evaluation of Uganda’s Strategy. Kampala: MoFPED.
- Nwagwu, N.A. (1976) “The Vocational Aspirations and Expectations of African Students.” *The Vocational Aspect of Education*, 28: 71, 111-115. See <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10408347308000701>
- PELUM Uganda (2010) Is Government Doing Enough to Support Agricultural Development in Uganda? A Review and Analysis of the Agricultural Sector Budgets at National and Local Government Levels (FY 2005/06 – 2009/10). Kampala: PELUM.
- Rank, M.R. and Hirschl, T.A. (2010) Estimating The Life Course Dynamics of Asset Poverty. CSD Working Papers No. 10-25. Washington University in St. Louis: Center for Social Development.
- Sherraden, M. (1991). *Assets and the poor*. Armonk, New York: M.E. Sharpe.
- Tripney, J., Hombrados, J., Newman, M., Hovish, K., Brown, C., steinka-Fry, K., and Wilkey, E. (2013) Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Interventions to Improve Employability and Employment of Young People in Low- and Middle-income Countries: A systematic Review. *Campbell Systematic Review* 2013:9. The Campbell Collaboration.
- UBOS (2012) Statistical Abstract. Kampala.
- World Bank (2012) World Development Report 2013: Jobs. New York: Oxford University Press.